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Challenges and opportunities to support community-based coastal and marine management through participatory mapping

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He mihi

I orea te tuatara ka patu ki waho

A problem is solved by continuing to find solutions

Mapping with Communities Workshop

Overview

- examples of participatory mapping from Aotearoa New Zealand (NZ)
- modalities for participatory approaches
 - public crowdsourcing
 - co-design
 - community-led
- enabling platforms
- lessons learned from NZ examples

Public crowdsourcing

General approach

- researcher-led projects engaging the public in making observations or contributing to image analysis.

Examples: image analysis

- Penguin Watch
- Spyfish
- Shark Spy

Examples: public observations

- Litter Intelligence
- Project Hotspot

Litter Intelligence

- NGO-led national litter monitoring programme launched 2018 by Sustainable Coastlines in collaboration with Stats NZ and Department of Conservation.
- provides open, scientifically rigorous litter data from survey sites around the country.
- methodology uses a localised adaptation of UNEP guidelines.

Objectives include

- enabling communities to collect data, gain insights and take action.
- implemented alongside the [Litter Intelligence Education Programme](#) designed for training educators to help students learn about pollution issues, become citizen scientists, identify real-world actions.

<https://litterintelligence.org/>

Data, insights and action for a litter-free world.

EXPLORE DATA or Search Data...

Stormwater		
390	1227	102
Average items per 1,000m ²	Average items per 1,000m ²	Average items per catchpit

34.7k	2951	550
VOLUNTEER HOURS	SURVEYS COMPLETED	SURVEY AREAS

Project Hotspot

- captures public observations of four coastal threatened species (orca, reef heron, little blue penguin and NZ fur seal).
- collects information to species distribution projects for each species hosted on iNaturalist.

Objectives include

- using the information to better protect these species and their habitats.
- implemented alongside a [schools education programme](#) that addresses:
 - Where are the hotspots for these species?
 - Why do these hotspots occur?
 - What are the greatest threats to these species and habitats?

Stats

Totals	Most Observations	Most Species	Most Observed Species
1861 Observations »	ingerp 381 observations	jacqui-nz 3 species	Kororā (Little Blue Penguin) 1849 observations
4 Species »	micaelb 200 observations	littleblue2 2 species	Weka 1 observation
288 People »	nig-motu 150 observations	mrr 1 species	European Rabbit 1 observation
	nikotgeorge 145 observations	deniswross 1 species	Red-billed Gull 1 observation
	emily_r 83 observations	c_michael_hagan 1 species	

Co-designed

General approach

- researcher-supported projects designed in collaboration with community.
- collaboration can involve a co-design process or an adaptable toolkit that is further contextualised by the community.

Examples: co-design process

- Curious Minds

Examples: adaptable toolkit

- Whitebait Watch

**A community guide to finding
īnanga spawning sites**

Curious Minds

- Government funding stream to promote science in society.
- individual projects are co-designed to meet needs or answer questions of interest to community.
- centered on community co-creation and meaningful two-way engagement¹.

Objectives include

- improving NZers ability to use science to make informed decisions.
- increased knowledge and visibility of different research methodologies, including kaupapa Māori approaches and Pacific-centred research methods.
- enabling communities and respond to their needs.

A NATION OF CURIOUS MINDS

HE WHENUA HIHIRI I TE MAHARA

**A NATIONAL STRATEGIC PLAN
FOR SCIENCE IN SOCIETY**

¹ Metcalf & Style (2019). *The American Journal of Bioethics*, 19(8), 40-43.

Curious Minds

- supported a wide range of participatory science and mapping projects, often to fill knowledge gaps or create educational initiatives.
- mostly funded small pilot projects (>20k budget) with limited life spans (e.g., 1-2 years).

CURIOUS MINDS

PARTICIPATORY SCIENCE PLATFORM AT A GLANCE

COMMUNITY GROUPS HAVE COLLABORATED WITH

70

DIFFERENT SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY EXPERTS

30

PROJECTS FUNDED

SCHOOLS INVOLVED IN LOCAL RESEARCH

>1000

PEOPLE ENGAGED IN SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY

12

SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY DISCIPLINES UNDER INVESTIGATION

DISTRIBUTION OF COMMUNITIES ENGAGED IN PARTICIPATORY SCIENCE PROJECTS

\$520,000

DISTRIBUTED IN TARANAKI

Whitebait Watch

- NGO-led project co-designed with partner community groups.
- centered around creation of a guide for community-based surveys to find fish spawning sites and a supporting database².

Components include

- 'How to' guides
- field sheets + data entry guide
- case studies with co-design partners
- curriculum links for educational applications

² Orchard (2022).

**A community guide to finding
inanga spawning sites**

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Community-led

General approach

- community initiated, community-led investigations.
- projects often emergent, e.g., in response to local needs³.
- may be supported by pre-existing research, technology or relationships with formally-trained scientists (either paid or unpaid).

Examples:

- CatMap
- Water clarity monitoring by Cashmere Stream Care Group⁴

³ Palacin et al. (2020). *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 5(1), 1–20.

⁴ Challies & Orchard (2025).

Benefits of community stream care:

Insights from a case study of the
Cashmere Stream Care Group
in Ōtautahi Christchurch

February 2025

Prepared by: **Ed Challies** and **Shane Orchard**
Waterways Centre, University of Canterbury

CatMap

- leverages GPS technology.
- community-led implementation in response to interest or perceived utility.
- data is used at very local (household) scale.

Components include

- access to technology (GPS tracking collars)
- 'How to' guides
- case studies of previous examples

Enabling platforms

Project	Data collection	Data storage
Litter Intelligence	bespoke / proprietary system	bespoke / proprietary system
Project Hotspot	iNaturalist App	iNaturalist customised project
Curious Minds projects	various approaches	iNaturalist and others
Whitebait Watch	iNaturalist App	iNaturalist customised project
CatMap	GPS tracker	none required!

Lessons learned from NZ examples

Key insights

- more localised and contextualised can equate to smaller potential datasets ... but that's ok!
 - quality (and integrity, equity ...) over quantity of data collected!
- local data uses may not require complicated storage or sharing arrangements.
- platforms that accommodate or facilitate end-user customisation can support local communities in generating and analysing geospatial data.
 - participant aspirations and data sovereignty are paramount.
- recognising and supporting the diverse motivations for participatory science is an overarching consideration for participatory mapping⁵

⁵ Orchard (2019). *Pacific Conservation Biology*, 25(4), 342-344.

References

- ¹ Metcalf, V. J., & Style, R. L. (2019). Cultural considerations in citizen health science and the case for community-based approaches. *The American Journal of Bioethics*, 19(8), 40-43. doi:10.1080/15265161.2019.1619874
- ² Orchard, S. (2022). *A community guide to finding īnanga spawning sites*. ISBN 978-0-473-63517-8. University of Canterbury. 32pp. Available at <https://bit.ly.inangaspawningguide>.
- ³ Palacin, V., Gilbert, S., Orchard, S., Eaton, A., Ferrario, M. A., & Happonen, A. (2020). Drivers of participation in digital citizen science: case studies on Järviwiki and Safecast. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 5(1), 1–20. doi:10.5334/cstp.290
- ⁴ Challies, E., & Orchard, S. (2025). *Benefits of community stream care: Insights from a case study of the Cashmere Stream Care Group in Ōtautahi Christchurch*. Waterways Centre for Freshwater Management, University of Canterbury. 47pp. Available at <https://hdl.handle.net/10092/108226>.
- ⁵ Orchard, S. (2019). Growing citizen science for conservation to support diverse project objectives and the motivations of volunteers. *Pacific Conservation Biology*, 25(4), 342-344. doi:10.1071/PC18011

Ngā mihinui kia koutou

Thanks for your interest!

Contact details

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